

Optimum Lignin Oil - Finding the most suitable feedstock to replace cycloalkanes in Sustainable Aviation Fuel (SAF)

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Abstract: This study highlights the effectiveness of hydrodeoxygenation (HDO) in converting lignin oils from Eucalyptus, Poplar, and Pine wood, derived from reductive catalytic fractionation (RCF), into renewable cycloalkanes for jet fuel. Using a low-cost Ni₂P/SiO₂ catalyst, the process achieved yields of 91 %, 84 %, and 75 % of renewable cycloalkanes respectively. In addition, the process exhibited high selectivity towards a specific range of hydrocarbons mostly present in aviation fuel (C₉ to C₁₅), with values of 70%, 60% and 62% for the three feedstocks, respectively, showcasing the potential for high-value fuel production. The research underscores the importance of modifying lignin oil properties through various chemo-catalytic biorefining pathways, which significantly influence the quality of the produced blend via HDO. These findings provide valuable insights into optimizing feedstock characteristics for improved jet-range hydrocarbon production.

Globally, the demand for fossil-based jet fuel in commercial aviation is expected to rise due to population growth and increased travel, with a projected 32% increase by 2050.^[1] To mitigate greenhouse gas emissions during this period, a renewable alternative to conventional jet fuel is essential. Sustainable aviation fuel (SAF) presents a viable solution, as it can reduce carbon emissions without necessitating modifications to existing engines and infrastructure. Currently, most approved SAFs are derived from vegetable and animal lipids, primarily consisting of n- and iso-alkanes, which can partially replace conventional jet fuel.^[2–8] However, these fuels typically contain a specific blend of aromatics, cycloalkanes, iso-alkanes, and n-alkanes ranging from C₈ to C₁₈.^[6,8,9] Importantly, most of the composition of conventional aviation fuel includes molecules with 9 to 15 carbons, making hydrocarbons in this carbon range crucial for an high value synthetic blend.^[7,9] To achieve fully synthesized (100%) SAF, renewable aromatics and cycloalkanes must be integrated into the fuel mix (ESI, Fig S1 and Table S11).^[7,9] Simultaneously, the aviation industry aims to reduce aromatic content due to their role in contrail formation, soot generation, and particulate emissions.^[7,8,10] Cycloalkanes, with their high energy density, could effectively replace or reduce aromatic

concentrations. However, a minimum concentration of aromatics is required to ensure compatibility with the engines used in modern aircrafts.^[7] Therefore, investigating alternative, sustainable feedstocks for renewable cycloalkanes is crucial for supplying 100% SAF to current aircraft. However, no established process currently exists for producing renewable aromatics or cycloalkanes to enhance available SAF.^[6]

In this context, lignin stands out as the largest natural source of renewable aromatic compounds, making it an ideal feedstock to replace petroleum-derived counterparts. Lignin is a branched biopolymer with a complex structure, consisting of phenolic units connected by ether and carbon-carbon linkages.^[11–13] It is found in both woody and herbaceous biomass, constituting about 15–30% of their composition.^[11–13]

Despite its significant potential, lignin has primarily been regarded as an industrial waste product, a perspective rooted in the paper industry. Here, lignin is often treated as a secondary component that contributes to biomass recalcitrance, hindering the valorization of carbohydrates from lignocellulosic biomass (i.e., cellulose and hemicellulose).^[11–15] Recently, innovative processes have been developed to address the challenges posed by conventional lignocellulose delignification methods, such as Kraft and Organosolv. These traditional treatments typically irreversibly alter lignin's structure, diminishing its chemical reactivity for depolymerization. This occurs mainly due to repolymerization reactions, which result in condensed lignin structures with more carbon-carbon linkages than the original biopolymer.^[12–16] In contrast, new biorefining methods aim to enhance the value of both lignin and carbohydrates.^[12–15,17–20] Among these, Reductive Catalytic Fractionation (RCF) is one of the most promising techniques, facilitating a shift from traditional approaches to a modern biorefinery concept known as the lignin-first approach.^[12–15,21–24] In RCF, most lignin is extracted from biomass as lignin oil, a low-molecular-weight mixture primarily composed of monomers, with some dimers, trimers, and larger oligomers.^[12–15,21–24] However, the high oxygen content of RCF lignin-oil limit its direct use as a drop-in fuel. Therefore, a deoxygenation step is required

to convert it into an oxygen-free hydrocarbon pool suitable for fuel applications. Catalytic hydrodeoxygenation (HDO) emerged as a promising method for converting lignin-derived phenolic compounds into hydrocarbons, with significant progress reflected in recent studies, particularly for RCF-derived lignin-oil.^[25-29] For example, Stone et al. converted poplar wood lignin-oil into jet-range aromatics using a two-stage continuous catalytic HDO with molybdenum carbide as the catalyst. In this study, 86% of the theoretical carbon recovery was achieved with high selectivity (87.5%) towards aromatics.^[25] Adler et al. explored the use of lignin-oil from the RCF of poplar wood, achieving 90% of carbon recovery after HDO, varying product selectivity (gasoline, diesel and aviation fuel), adjusting hydrotreatment temperatures. The study also discusses the potential of higher lignin-oil cuts (dimers and larger oligomers) as biofuel precursors but does not address the challenges associated with their conversion.^[26]

In another study, Verma et al. pointed out the advantages of lower lignin oil cuts (monomers and dimers) over larger oligomers for SAF. Still, the authors did not address the complexities behind converting high molecular weight molecules via HDO. Nevertheless, in their study, HDO of birchwood lignin oil resulted in a hydrocarbon blend with a 75% aviation cut.^[27] Gao et al. demonstrated the solvent free HDO of eucalyptus-derived lignin oil into cycloalkanes with 32.7 wt% yield and high selectivity for C₆ to C₁₀ cyclic hydrocarbons using an atomically dispersed Pt-polyoxometalate catalyst under 20 bar H₂ at 150°C for 24 hours.^[28] Guan et al. reported an 80.1% molar yield and over 99% selectivity for smaller hydrocarbons (C₆ to C₁₀) using Rh/Nb₂O₅ as a catalyst, demonstrating significant carbon-carbon cracking for larger molecules in the lignin-oil under certain reaction conditions.^[29]

Other research groups have also explored different lignin feedstocks for HDO. For example, Cao et al. investigated the catalytic upgrading of poplar and spruce lignin oils from Early-stage Catalytic Conversion of Lignin (ECCL) using a phosphided Ni/SiO₂ catalyst. They adjusted hydrogen pressure and reaction temperature to tune selectivity towards aromatics or aliphatics. While this study employed two distinct wood feedstocks (hardwood and softwood), it does not address the relationship between the chemical properties of the oils derived from different type of woods and the HDO products.^[30] Jia et al. reported lower HDO performance for Organosolv lignin compared to RCF lignin-oil with a phosphided Ni catalyst, but did not discuss the properties of Organosolv lignin that make it more difficult to convert.^[31] Meanwhile, Prof. Yang's group studied HDO of alkali-extracted corn stover lignin, which yielded only 30 wt% of hydrocarbons.^[32-33] In a related work, Ruan et al. carried out the HDO of alkali-diluted corn stover lignin to generate liquid products with higher molecular weight hydrocarbons such as tri-cycloparaffins and tetra-cycloparaffins. This could be attributed to the properties of the technical lignin, although this issue was not discussed.^[34] These works highlight the challenges of converting technical lignin through HDO.^[32-35]

Hèroguet et al. investigated the simultaneous depolymerization and HDO of aldehyde-stabilized lignin extracted from beech wood. They emphasized the importance of solubility for efficient HDO and proposed using dioxane as an alternative solvent to improve

solubility. However, the simultaneous depolymerization and HDO of aldehyde-stabilized lignin achieved a maximum deoxygenation of 50%, with selectivity towards mono-cycloalkanes, yielding a maximum of 15 wt%.^[36]

These studies collectively highlight the potential of HDO for producing valuable hydrocarbons from lignin-oil or isolated lignins. Various lignin feedstocks have been explored under different conditions, demonstrating the potential of HDO to produce valuable hydrocarbons for fuel production.^[25-39]

However, there is a notable lack of evidence or conclusive interpretations regarding the relationship between the type of lignin oil and the HDO performance. This gap is particularly significant, considering the variations in lignin oils that can arise from different biorefining methods, feedstocks, and processing parameters.^[25-39] In this context, this comprehensive investigation aims to provide detailed insights into how critical properties of lignin oils influence the quality of the products obtained after HDO. To identify the most suitable oil as a feedstock for sustainable cyclic hydrocarbons in the jet range, it is crucial to clarify two fundamental aspects. First, an effective biorefining method for isolating lignin oil from lignocellulosic biomass needs to be identified. Second, it is essential to understand how the properties of lignin oil influence the quality of the HDO products. This requires demonstrating the relationship between lignin oil chemistry and the properties of the HDO products, enabling a synergistic improvement of both. In this study, we demonstrate that quantifying the differences in lignin oil properties allows for the development of an effective methodology for producing cyclic hydrocarbons suitable for SAF. To achieve this, we utilized various feedstocks, catalysts, and biorefining methods to derive lignin oils with distinct chemical characteristics, enabling us to optimize the HDO performance. Table 1 presents an overview of the biorefining methods, feedstocks, and catalysts used for the series of lignin oils examined in this study.

Initially, six RCF-derived lignin oils were produced from three different feedstocks such as poplar, pine, and eucalyptus using two catalysts (Ru/C and Pd/C) under state-of-the-art reaction conditions (ESI Section A.2.1[†]). The selected raw materials exhibit variations in the content of syringyl (S) and guaiacyl (G) units, which are known to significantly influence the monomer content and average molecular weight (Mw) distribution of the oils in the RCF products.^[14,19,40] Among the feedstocks studied, pine wood, belonging to the conifer family (softwood), has a higher G unit content. In contrast, eucalyptus and poplar wood belong to the deciduous family (hardwood) and contain more S units. As a result, the quantified phenolic monomers in the lignin oils from hardwoods (poplar and eucalyptus) are primarily composed of G and S units, while G units dominate the phenolic monomers in the lignin oils from softwood (pine) (ESI Figure S2[†]). Additionally, the higher G unit content in softwood (pine) leads to a greater proportion of dimers, trimers, and oligomers in the RCF lignin oil compared to hardwoods (eucalyptus and poplar), where the monomer content is higher.^[40] Finally, Early-stage Catalytic Conversion of Lignin (ECCL) oil, as well as Organosolv lignin from poplar wood, and Organosolv lignin from birch wood were obtained from reported biorefineries, under varying reaction conditions (Table 1, ESI Sections A.2.2, 2.3, and 2.4[†]).^[30,41]

Table 1. Set of different lignin oils synthesized and used in this work.* is reproduced from reference [30] and ** is reproduced from reference [41].

Code	Biorefining	Feedstock (Type)	Catalyst	T [°C]	H ₂ [bar]	Solvent
RCF Poplar Ru/C	RCF	Poplar (Hard wood)	Ru/C	235	30	MeOH
RCF Poplar Pd/C	RCF	Poplar (Hard wood)	Pd/C	235	30	MeOH
RCF Pine Ru/C	RCF	Pine (Soft wood)	Ru/C	235	30	MeOH
RCF Pine Pd/C	RCF	Pine (Soft wood)	Pd/C	235	30	MeOH
RCF Eucalyptus Ru/C	RCF	Eucalyptus (Hard wood)	Ru/C	235	30	MeOH
RCF Eucalyptus Pd/C	RCF	Eucalyptus (Hard wood)	Pd/C	235	30	MeOH
ECCL Poplar Raney Ni	*ECCL	Poplar (Hard wood)	Raney Ni	180	no	H ₂ O and 2-PrOH
Organosolv 1	Organosolv	Poplar (Hard wood)	No	235	no	MeOH
Organosolv 2	**Organosolv	Birch (Hard wood)	No	105	no	Formic Acid

Subsequently, the HDO of the produced lignin oils was performed using a Ni₂P/SiO₂ catalyst at 300 °C for 22 hours under 50 MPa of hydrogen pressure (ESI Section A.6[†]).

The presented reaction conditions for HDO have been selected in order to have the highest selectivity towards cycloalkanes rather than aromatics, and to avoid significant carbon-carbon cracking with the selected catalyst as reported elsewhere.^[30]

The HDO products were analyzed using GC-MS/FID (ESI Section A.7[†]), confirming the formation of a wide range of cycloalkanes, with propyl cyclohexane as the predominant component. Notably, most of the components were identified by comparing the deconvoluted mass spectra from GC-MS with the NIST library. The hydrocarbons were then classified based on the carbon number, enabling the determination of the aviation cut present in the liquid products (Section A.8 of the ESI[†]). A list of all identified compounds, divided by their carbon number, is provided in Table S13[†]. To further support the claim on the aviation cut present in the liquid products after HDO (Table S13 and Figure S3[†]), GCxGC-EI-TOFMS analysis was conducted for one of the best-performing sample (RCF Poplar Ru/C) and the results are present in Figure S4[†]. In addition, GC-MS analysis allowed to confirm the absence of oxygenated compounds in the products. However, to support this conclusion, elemental analysis was carried out on all the HDO products from different lignin feedstocks (Section A.9 of the ESI[†]) and the degree of deoxygenation was found to be at least 88% for all the feedstocks (Table S14[†]). The yield of hydrocarbons present in the products was calculated with GC-FID, with the methodology explained in details in the Section A.8 of the ESI[†]. For the sake of clarity in analysis, this study reports the cumulative yield of cycloalkanes (total yield) expressed as weight percentages relative to the theoretical maximum, calculated based on elemental analysis, for all the different oils (ESI Section A.11, Tables S2–S10[†]).

In addition, the jet-range selectivity is employed as parameter to evaluate the discrimination of the HDO towards a crucial range of hydrocarbons for conventional aviation fuel (C₉ to C₁₅).^[7,9] This parameter is defined as the ratio of the cumulative yield of C₉ to C₁₅ hydrocarbons (relative to the theoretical maximum) to the cumulative jet yield (C₈ to C₁₈), for all the oils used. All the lignin oils used in this study were compared based on their HDO performance towards a specific range of selected hydrocarbons. The jet-range selectivity helps to highlight the quality of different produced blend of cycloalkanes to serve as replacement for conventional aviation fuels employed in current aircrafts. As illustrated in Figure 1, lignin oils derived from RCF biorefining with Ru/C as the catalyst demonstrated high total yields alongside high selectivity of jet-range hydrocarbons. Specifically, the selectivity of jet-range hydrocarbons decreased in the following order: RCF Eucalyptus Ru/C (70.5%) > RCF Pine Ru/C (61.5%) > RCF Poplar Ru/C (60%). In contrast, lignin oils obtained from RCF biorefining using Pd/C, as well as ECCL Poplar Raney Ni and Organosolv 1 lignin oils, exhibited relatively high total yields but lower selectivity of jet-range hydrocarbons. Additionally, Organosolv 2 showed the poorest HDO performance regarding the total yield with a lower selectivity for jet-range hydrocarbons. Notably, RCF Eucalyptus Ru/C, RCF Pine Ru/C, and RCF Poplar Ru/C emerged as the top feedstocks (Figure 1). These findings suggest that the HDO performance of different lignin oils is closely linked to their intrinsic physical and chemical properties. The heterogeneity of lignin oils, characterized by diverse chemical linkages, functional groups, and molecular weights, likely influences their efficiency as HDO feedstocks. Consequently, a detailed study was conducted to elucidate how the properties of different oils affect the yield of jet-range hydrocarbons.

Figure 1. The yield of hydrocarbons is expressed as a weight percentage relative to the theoretical maximum of the original oils. The selectivity of jet-range hydrocarbons is expressed as the ratio between the yield of C₉ to C₁₅ hydrocarbons and the jet yield (C₈ to C₁₈). The yields are determined through GC analysis. RCF-derived oils are indicated in red, while non-RCF-derived oils are shown in blue. Reaction conditions: Lignin oil (0.1 g), Ni₂P/SiO₂ (0.08 g), Temperature (300 °C), H₂ Pressure (50 bar), Reaction Time (22 h).

To understand the properties of lignin oil that influence HDO performance, a correlation analysis was conducted to identify the relationship between quantifiable properties (e.g., syringyl and guaiacyl content, monomer content, and hydroxyl groups) and selectivity towards jet-range hydrocarbons following HDO.

First, to better comprehend how the chosen feedstock affects HDO performance, we established a correlation between the syringyl content of various lignin oils and the resulting selectivity to jet-range hydrocarbons (Figure 2). The content of S and G units in the lignin oils was quantified using ¹H-¹³C HSQC NMR, as previously reported.^[40] The difference in S content for these samples (Figure 2) aligns with the expectations based on the selected feedstocks. As previously mentioned, a higher quantity of monomers in RCF products corresponds with an increase in syringyl units in the feedstock. Consequently, woody biomass such as eucalyptus and poplar (hardwoods) exhibit a significantly high weight percentage of monomers in the derived lignin oil (ESI Figure S5[†]). On the other hand, lignin oil derived from pine (softwood) presents a lower content of monomers compared to Eucalyptus and Poplar (ESI Figure S5[†]) and is enriched with bigger molecules (e.g., dimers and trimers) due to the low content of S unit. As shown in Figure 2, RCF Eucalyptus Ru/C shows the highest selectivity of jet-range hydrocarbons with an elevated syringyl content, suggesting that the HDO is more efficient when lignin oil enriched in monomers is used as feedstock. However, RCF Pine Ru/C shows a close selectivity towards jet-range hydrocarbons to RCF Poplar Ru/C despite its scarcer syringyl content. In this context, Figure 2 proves the efficiency of the HDO in converting both monomers and bigger molecules (e.g., dimers and trimers) towards cycloalkanes in the jet-range, when an efficient catalytic process is designed. In a future scenario where lignin could serve as feedstock to replace currently employed jet

fuel, it is important to establish a process which is not strictly selective on the type of feedstock employed in the process, as this could represent an issue in the selective harvesting of woody biomass. However, Figure 2 shows how the criterions for a successful HDO towards jet-range hydrocarbons, lie in other aspects of the biorefining process, as evidenced by feedstocks like RCF Eucalyptus Pd/C, RCF Poplar Pd/C and RCF Pine Pd/C. Figure 2 clearly illustrates that RCF lignin oils produced using Pd/C as a catalyst consistently yield lower jet-range hydrocarbons than other RCF oils, regardless of their S/G ratio. These results indicate that the catalyst used during RCF biorefining significantly affects the properties of lignin oils, which in turn influences their HDO performance. Specifically, the two catalysts (Ru/C and Pd/C) used in RCF biorefining are known to impact the selectivity of saturated end-units in monomers, dimers, trimers, and oligomers. Generally, under certain reaction conditions, Pd/C tends to increase the selectivity of propanol end-units in the lignin oil, while Ru/C is more selective toward propyl end-units, (ESI Figure S6[†]).^[42] When HDO was performed on lignin oils derived from RCF conducted with Ru/C and Pd/C catalysts, a significant difference in performance was observed, with the RCF lignin oils produced using Ru/C showing the highest selectivity of jet-range hydrocarbons together with high total yield (Figure 1). A plausible explanation for this behavior could be the selective transformation of propanol-substituted monomers in lignin oil into C₈ hydrocarbons after HDO, facilitated by dehydrogenation and subsequent decarbonylation reactions to CO (Scheme 1A), contrary to what happens in propyl substituted monomers (Scheme 1B).

Figure 2. Jet-range hydrocarbons selectivity as a function of different syringyl (S) content in different lignin – oils. The jet-range selectivity is defined as the ratio of the cumulative yield of C₉ to C₁₅ to the cumulative jet yield (C₈ to C₁₈). In red are displayed the RCF derived oils; In blue are displayed the non-RCF-derived oils; Reaction conditions: Lignin oil (0.1 g), Ni₂P/SiO₂ (0.08 g), Temperature (300 °C), H₂ Pressure (50 bar), Reaction Time (22 h).

As a result, lignin oil with a higher proportion of oxygenated end-units (γ -OH) is more likely to lose an additional carbon during HDO, leading to HDO products enriched in C₈ hydrocarbons, less preferred in the current employed aviation fuels compared to C₉ to C₁₅ hydrocarbons. To validate this hypothesis, we further analyzed the impact of terminal oxygenated end units (γ -OH) on density of jet-range hydrocarbons following HDO treatment (Figure 3). The amount of γ -OH was quantified using ¹H-¹³C HSQC NMR to support the proposed mechanism.^[40] Figure 3 illustrates a linear correlation, showing that selectivity of jet-range hydrocarbons decreases as the amount of γ -OH in lignin oils increases. To further investigate this relationship, synthetic mixtures (M1, M2, and M3) were prepared by gradually blending two different lignin oils (RCF Poplar Ru/C and RCF Poplar Pd/C) to systematically adjust the oxygenated end-units. Mixture M1 consists of 75 wt% Poplar Ru/C oil and 25 wt% Poplar Pd/C oil, M2 is a 50/50 wt% blend, and M3 contains 25 wt% Poplar Ru/C oil and 75 wt% Poplar Pd/C oil (Figures S7 and S8[†]). For these synthetic blends, a similar linear relationship between the amount of γ -OH units and the selectivity to jet-range hydrocarbons is

observed (Figure 3). These findings indicate that the catalyst used during RCF biorefining, with specific reaction conditions, significantly influences the chemical properties of lignin oils, thereby affecting their HDO performance. Notably, lignin oil with fewer γ -OH end units is more suitable for producing C₉ and larger hydrocarbons. The presence of terminal γ -OH end units shifts selectivity toward C_{<9} hydrocarbons rather than C₉-C₁₅, negatively impacting the production of high quality SAF. These results are the first to demonstrate how tuning the chemical properties of RCF oil can optimize the conversion of lignocellulosic biomass to jet fuel. Furthermore, it is essential to recognize how variations in the chemical composition of lignin oils can be brought in several ways, such as through the use of different catalysts, as discussed in this manuscript, or by modifying the biorefining conditions in terms of solvent, temperature, or gaseous environment. For example, in the study by Galkin et.al., the selectivity of RCF products with a Pd/C catalyst was tuned towards less oxygenated compounds, including propenyl and propyl substituted molecules in a hydrogen-free RCF process, using a mixture of EtOH/H₂O as solvent at 210°C.^[43]

Scheme 1. A) Proposed mechanism for the transformation of propanol-derived lignin monomers into C₈ hydrocarbons. B) Proposed mechanism for the conversion of propyl-derived lignin monomers into C₉ hydrocarbons.

Figure 3. Jet-range hydrocarbon selectivity as a function of the percentage of γ -OH in different lignin oils. The percentage of γ -OH units is determined using ^1H - ^{13}C HSQC NMR, with native aromatic units serving as an internal standard, as previously reported by our group. In the figure, RCF-derived oils are shown in red, non-RCF-derived oils in blue, and synthetic mixtures in green, with a color gradient indicating the percentage of each oil in the mixture. Reaction conditions: Lignin oil (0.1 g), $\text{Ni}_2\text{P}/\text{SiO}_2$ (0.08 g), Temperature (300 °C), H_2 Pressure (50 bar), Reaction Time (22 h).

Furthermore, as illustrated in Figure 3, oils produced through other biorefining methods exhibit relatively low selectivity for jet-range hydrocarbons, even with their low γ -OH content. For example, ECCL Poplar Raney Ni achieves a total hydrocarbon yield of 78 wt%, yet its selectivity to jet-range hydrocarbons is only 29.6 % after HDO. In contrast, Organosolv 1 has a total yield of 67.4 % and a selectivity to jet-range hydrocarbons of 42%. Notably, the technical lignin from Organosolv 2 show a selectivity of jet-range hydrocarbons of 44.8%, but achieves the lowest total yield of only 27 wt% (Figure 1). To understand this discrepancy, we examined the influence of lignin oil properties from established biorefining processes on HDO performance. By comparing the properties of lignin oils obtained from these methods with those derived from RCF, we can hypothesize the factors that may limit their conversion into hydrocarbons. Specifically, GPC data (ESI Figure S9[†]) indicates that the high weight-average molecular weight of the non-RCF lignin oils contributes to their lower performance. In this regard, the Mw (excluding monomers from the calculation) for Organosolv 1, ECCL Poplar Raney Ni, and Organosolv 2 is 1986, 2340, and 5950 g mol^{-1} , respectively. The high Mw of these lignin oils may impede their solubility in alkane environments, such as dodecane, during HDO, thereby affecting their efficient conversion to a specific range of hydrocarbons. To test this hypothesis, solubility assessments of four different oils (RCF Poplar Ru/C, Organosolv 1, ECCL Poplar Raney Ni, and Organosolv 2) were conducted in refluxed dodecane under comparable conditions (ESI Section A.12[†]). Figure 4 illustrates the weight percentage of soluble and insoluble fractions relative to the initial amount of lignin oil. The results reveal that the soluble

fraction is highest for RCF Poplar Ru/C at 90 wt%, followed by ECCL Poplar Raney Ni (75 wt%), Organosolv 1 (72 wt%), and Organosolv 2 (38 wt%). These findings support the hypothesis that the higher Mw of lignin oils from alternative biorefining processes contributes to their lower solubility, ultimately leading to reduced performance as feedstock for HDO.

Additionally, this indicates that RCF-derived oils serve as superior feedstocks compared to those obtained through other biorefining methods. However, the high Mw may also pose challenges for the conversion of these oils into hydrocarbons, affecting factors such as diffusion and accessibility to catalyst pores, which are reflected in their low solubility in dodecane. This underscores the importance of selecting the appropriate biorefining technique for successful jet-range hydrocarbon production through HDO. However, ECCL Poplar Raney Ni also presents a relatively higher content of γ -OH (Figure 3) compared to RCF-derived lignin oil with Ru/C as the catalyst, which may, along with the high Mw, contribute to a lower selectivity for jet-range hydrocarbons. Therefore, Organosolv 2 presents the lowest total yield due to its highest Mw (5950 g mol^{-1}) and lowest solubility (Figure 4). Consequently, it has the lowest HDO performance despite its low γ -OH content.

Moreover, Figures 2 and 3 clearly indicate that Organosolv 1 exhibits a lower selectivity for jet-range hydrocarbons, notwithstanding its high S content. The feedstock chosen for Organosolv 1 is poplar, which results in a high S content in the derived lignin oil (Figure 2). Additionally, the absence of a catalyst during the biorefining process can lead to re-condensation reactions, resulting in an oil with a high Mw and a reduced

proportion of monomers. As shown in Figure 4, these factors contribute to solubility issues, which explain the lower conversion to jet-range hydrocarbons of Organosolv 1 compared to RCF Eucalyptus Ru/C and RCF Poplar Ru/C. The insoluble part of the RCF lignin oil in alkane (product) is lowest when produced from poplar using Ru/C catalyst, but still contributes to non-quantitative hydrocarbon yield. To gain additional structural information on the insoluble fraction of RCF Poplar Ru/C, it was analyzed by GPC and ^1H - ^{13}C HSQC NMR (Figure S10, S11 and S12[†]). Shortly, the solid lignin, that is soluble in acetone, has an average molecular weight M_w of around 3600 g mol^{-1} , and contains mainly the polar β ,1-, β -5, and β - β - γ -OH interlinkages and γ -OH arene substituents.

Figure 4. Solubility (in wt%) of lignin oils from different biorefining methods in dodecane. Solubility test conditions: Dodecane (22 mL); Temperature (220 °C); Lignin oil (0.150 g); Time (1 h); rpm (700).

Given the wide variety of produced lignin oils, an initial reaction time of 22 hours was selected to prevent any discrepancies in the conversion of the feedstocks during HDO. Once the optimal feedstock type (viz. RCF Poplar Ru/C) was identified, we further examined the effect of reaction time (2, 5, and 22 hours) on HDO performance. As shown in Figure 5, the total hydrocarbon yield obtained after HDO processing of RCF Poplar Ru/C for 22 and 2 hours was comparable. This indicates that the HDO contact time could be reduced further to optimize the process. Nevertheless, there is a minimum threshold below which the hydrocarbon yield becomes suboptimal for HDO.

In conclusion, lignin oils were upgraded using an economical $\text{Ni}_2\text{P}/\text{SiO}_2$ catalyst to produce renewable C_8 - C_{18} cycloalkanes, with particular attention to the production of C_9 to C_{15} hydrocarbons, which are most suitable for fully synthesized SAF. This study marks the first demonstration that the HDO performance of lignin oils can be enhanced by employing appropriate feedstocks, catalysts, and biorefining methods. Among the various lignin oils examined, RCF Eucalyptus Ru/C, RCF Poplar Ru/C, and RCF Pine Ru/C emerged as the most

effective feedstocks, yielding total yield of hydrocarbons (relative to the theoretical maximum) of 91 %, 84 %, and 75 %, respectively. In addition, these three feedstocks produced blends with high selectivity for jet-range hydrocarbons (70%, 60%, and 62%), significantly outperforming the other lignin oils tested. Generally, this study highlights that the selection of an appropriate feedstock (hardwood or softwood) is not critically important when an effective biorefining strategy is combined with efficient catalytic HDO.

Figure 5. The yield of hydrocarbons, expressed as a weight percentage relative to the theoretical maximum of the original oils, for HDO products of RCF Poplar Ru/C at different reaction time. Reaction conditions: Lignin oil (0.1 g), $\text{Ni}_2\text{P}/\text{SiO}_2$ (0.08 g), Temperature (300 °C), H_2 Pressure (50 bar).

Generally, under the selected reaction conditions, lignin oils with low γ -OH content, and higher alkane solubility (low M_w) are the most promising feedstocks for upgrading to jet fuel-range cyclic hydrocarbons (C_8 - C_{18}) with high selectivity towards a particular range of hydrocarbons (C_9 to C_{15}) suitable for aviation fuel.

This study establishes a fundamental relationship between the chemical composition of lignin oil and its HDO performance, suggesting that synergistic improvements in HDO efficiency can be achieved by modulating the chemical properties of lignin oil. This approach opens new pathways for the controlled synthesis of high-performance jet fuel components from lignocellulosic biomass.

Supporting Information

The authors have cited additional references within the Supporting Information.^[44, 45]

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